

POST-PROCESSING OF ANIONIC POLYAMIDE-6 COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Research on post-processing of anionic polyamide-6 composites was performed, consisting of two main areas of interest: the cure time and the anneal cycle. The cure time and annealing temperature proved to be the crucial parameters to increase the degree of crystallinity, minimise the residual stresses and hence improve the mechanical properties.

Keywords: Cure; Annealing; Thermoplastic Resin; Anionic Polyamide-6; Resin infusion

INTRODUCTION

In order to produce thicker and bigger thermoplastic composite parts for use in for example offshore wind turbine blades, the traditional melt processing technique needs to be substituted with a vacuum infusion process. To overcome the high resin viscosity of thermoplastics resins, a reactive resin system was used for the vacuum infusion of the anionic polyamide-6 (APA-6) composites. Thermoplastic composites exhibit several advantages over their thermoset counterparts: lower processing times, easy assembly of parts through welding, recyclability and high toughness.

In previous research on pure APA-6 [1], it was shown that the polymerisation process was completed within 30 minutes. At the end of polymerisation, however, the crystallisation is still in progress. As the properties of the resin are mainly driven by the level of crystallinity [1], the cure and/or annealing cycle may influence the composite properties significantly. By selecting the right curing and post-processing parameters, it is expected that the demoulding time can be optimised, residual stresses minimised and hence the neat resin and composite properties significantly improved. In this paper, the effect of the cure time will be studied as well as the influence of annealing parameters.

All the samples in this study were manufactured at a processing temperature of 180°C. At this temperature, polymerisation precedes crystallisation. When compared to lower processing temperatures, this processing temperature yields a low degree of crystallinity and has high residual stresses, due to thermal shrinkage [2] after a normal cure cycle. Therefore, it is thought that the post-cure cycle will have the largest effect when the samples are manufactured at this processing temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Resin

For the vacuum infusion of the anionic polyamide-6 thermoplastic laminates, a reactive resin mixture is used, which consists of three components: the anionic polymerisation grade ϵ -caprolactam monomer, the activator and the initiator which were all supplied by Brüggemann Chemicals, Germany.

Glass fibres

E-glass fibre mats are used to reinforce the APA-6 composites. The 8-harness satin weave E-glass fabrics (SS 0303 050, weave style 7781, 300 gram/m^2) were supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites bv., Nijverdal, The Netherlands.

Processing methods

Preparation of resin mixture

A special designed lab-scale mixing unit (Mini Mixing Unit 'MMU-TUDeft', Bronk Industrial b.v., The Netherlands), see Figure 1, is used to prepare the resin mixture for infusion under a nitrogen atmosphere and at a temperature of 110°C. After dispensing the volume needed for the infusion of a laminate into a buffer vessel, the resin is degassed for 5 minutes to remove N_2 dissolved in the mixture during storage in the MMU tanks..

Figure 1. Vacuum infusion set-up (from left to right: Mini Mixing Unit, buffer vessel, laminate and heating device, resin trap and vacuum pump).

Figure 2. Infrared panel as heating device for the laminate.

Production of test tubes

Glass test tubes with a diameter of 20mm and a length of 150 mm (Schott-Fiolax) were used to make pure resin samples. The test tubes were preheated and flushed with nitrogen before dispensing 50 ml of resin. They were then sealed to prevent moisture uptake and placed in an insulated oil bath at 180°C. After the cure cycle, they were quenched in room temperature water.

Infusion of laminates

A balanced, symmetric 12-ply laminate (25x29 cm^2) is prepared for vacuum infusion and is placed between two infrared panels as can be seen in Figure 2 and is heated to 180°C prior to infusion. After degassing, the resin is allowed to flow through the inlet

line-injection into the laminate. The resin injection and fibre compaction are achieved under vacuum. The vacuum is maintained during the cure cycle.

Analysis methods

Degree of conversion

To determine the degree of conversion (DOC) of the polymer, samples of the composite plate are taken at 5 cm from the resin inlet. After drying the samples at 50°C in a vacuum oven, they are weighed (m_{tot}). Next, the samples are refluxed overnight in demineralised water. After this process, the residue is dried and weighed again. As the monomer dissolves in the water, the mass loss can be attributed to the monomer (m_{mon}). Additionally the weight of the fibres needs to be measured. Therefore, the samples were burned off in a carbolite oven at 565°C for one hour; according to ASTM D 2584–02 and the fibre weight (m_{fib}) was obtained. The degree of conversion can then be calculated as follows:

$$\text{DOC} = \left(1 - \frac{m_{\text{mon}}}{m_{\text{tot}} - m_{\text{fib}}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

It should be taken into account that low molecular oligomers formed during polymerisation will also dissolve during the reflux process [3]. As these oligomers as well as the monomer do not have load carrying capabilities, Eq. 1 will give a good impression of the amount of non-load carrying substances in the composite but will thus not give the exact degree of conversion.

Degree of crystallinity

The degree of crystallinity (X_c) of the polymer are determined by means of a Perkin Elmer Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC). The disc-shaped samples (m_{sp}) of approximately 5 mg are taken from the laminate at the same location as the degree of conversion samples and are dried overnight. The samples were tested from 25°C to 240°C at a rate of 10°C per minute. The results had to be corrected for the fibre content and the degree of conversion of the sample. Therefore, the fibre content (m_{fib}) was determined by burning off the resin after the DSC test. The degree of crystallinity can now be calculated as follows:

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_{100}} \cdot \frac{m_{\text{sp}}}{m_{\text{sp}} - m_{\text{fib}}} \cdot \frac{1}{\text{DOC}/100} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

In which: ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy of the specimen [J/g]; ΔH_{100} is the melting enthalpy of a fully crystalline polyamide-6 = 190 J/g [4]. The third term in Eq. 2 is a correction factor for the degree of conversion of the sample.

Short-beam strength

The short-beam strength tests were conducted on a Zwick Roell 2 ton force machine according to the ASTM D2344 norm. The test specimens for the short-beam strength test were rectangular shaped: 16.2 x 5.4 x 2.7 mm³. From the maximum force (P_{max}), the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) can be calculated:

$$\text{ILSS} = 0.75 \times \frac{P_{\text{max}}}{b \times t} \quad (3)$$

In which b and t are the width and thickness of the specimen, respectively. A minimum of 5 specimens was tested. According to the ASTM Standard, the short-beam strength

test is suited for comparative testing of composite materials, provided that failures occur consistently in the same mode.

CURE TIME

The effect of the cure time is assessed on both neat resin and composites. For the neat resin, a broad spectrum of cure times was tested ranging from 15 to 120 minutes, with a 15 min interval with an extra data point at 180 min. Glass fibre reinforced APA-6 were cured at 30-60-90-120min, firstly to determine if the trends in material properties correlate to the neat resin samples and secondly to determine optimum cure time.

Pure resin

For the pure resin, it was seen that with increasing cure time, the degree of crystallinity rose, until a plateau was reached at approximately 100 minutes of curing, as can be seen in Figure 3. The cure time as researched by van Rijswijk et al. [1], had little effect on the degree of conversion between 30 and 45min, over a range of cure temperatures. The results from this research show a clear agreement in an approximately constant DOC of 92% between the 30 to 75min range. Figure 4 also shows an optimum in degree of conversion at the same cure time as for the degree of crystallinity. The almost 7% change in conversion observed over a cure time range of 75min to 120min clearly indicates that further conversion of monomer, at a cure temperature of 180°C, can take place for neat resin. After that, the degree of conversion decreases due to degradation of the polymer or due to a shift in the equilibrium reaction between the monomer and polymer.

Figure 3. Evolution of degree of crystallinity of pure resin in time.

Figure 4. Evolution of degree of conversion of pure resin in time.

Laminates

The effect of cure time on the laminate is greatly less significant for the degree of conversion, which proved to be almost constant at a value of $98.5\% \pm 0.3\%$. For the effect of cure time on the degree of crystallinity, Figure 5 shows a linear increase to a peak value of 36.5% at 90min and an almost constant peak crystallinity of 36% even at 120min. Figure 6 shows that the maximum short-beam strength is 77.4MPa, coinciding with the cure time of 90min for peak crystallinity.

Figure 5. Degree of crystallinity for different cure times

Figure 6. Short-beam strength for different cure times

The increase in crystallinity with cure time is in the same order of magnitude as for the pure resin. The increased crystallinity for both the pure resin and the laminate can be explained by the greater extent of primary crystallization that occurs during curing over the secondary crystallization that only initiates from subsequent cooling. It is known [1] that at higher processing temperature branching may occur in the resin. Branching causes a crystal type transition from α to γ structure [5, 6], which are two types of crystals with different levels of perfection. With an increased primary crystallization, a greater amount of the more perfect α crystals are formed, while γ or the less perfect α crystals formed during secondary crystallization make up a lower composition of the overall crystal structure. An inherently greater extent and perfection of the crystal structure in the polymer clearly would increase the strength of the polymer due to increased covalent bonds present.

It was observed that an optimal degree of crystallinity could be found and that this cure time corresponded to optimal mechanical properties (short-beam strength). Literature states that all semi-crystalline polymers have a direct relationship between the short-beam strength and the degree of crystallinity [7]. This direct relation further accounts for the results showing an increase in the short-beam strength of the laminate due to the increased crystallinity with cure time.

ANNEALING CONDITIONS

Initial cure times of 30 and 60 min were chosen for the research on annealing of APA-6 composites. As seen in the last paragraph, full crystallisation has not been reached yet for those cure times. It is expected that the crystallization behaviour will improve and the residual stresses will diminish during the annealing cycle.

Within this study, the cured laminate is cooled down to room temperature and removed from the mould, after which it is placed in an oven for the annealing cycle. Design of Experiments was used for the research in which the following parameters were studied: annealing time, annealing temperature and cooling rate.

Three important temperatures can be identified for annealing: the glass transition temperature T_g ($\approx 60-75^\circ\text{C}$), the crystallization temperature T_c ($\approx 160-175^\circ\text{C}$) and the melting temperature T_m ($\approx 210-220^\circ\text{C}$). Semi-crystalline materials are known to undergo additional crystallization when held at a temperature between its glass and

melting temperature. Conventional annealing is done at temperatures at or above T_c , leading to increased crystallinity and reduced toughness [8]. If embrittlement is undesirable, a lower temperature annealing can be effective. A lower annealing temperature reduces the heat energy requirements without extending annealing time and thus reducing the costs. The following temperatures were selected for this study: 100-150-175°C. The laminates were held at the annealing temperature for 2, 4 or 6 hours. Temperatures at or above 200°C will not be explored in this study as thermal and thermal-oxidative degradation is considerably high [9] and cannot be used practically especially with significant material discoloration.

After the annealing cycle, the laminate is subjected to a controlled cooling of either fast or slow rate. Fast cooling, is performed by removing the laminate from the oven and allowing it to cool naturally to room temperature. Slow cooling, is carried out by switching off the oven and allowing the laminate to cool inside the oven, with the oven ventilator opened.

ANNEALING RESULTS

Degree of conversion

For reinforced APA-6, the effect of reheating the polymer for a period of time is expected to increase the degree of conversion, improve the crystallinity by inducing favourable crystal type transition (from γ -crystals to α -crystals) [10] and remove imperfections in crystal structure. The degree of conversion, however, seemed to be constant for all laminates, complying with the results of van Rijswijk et al. [1], stating that the conversion of the APA-6 resin is completed within 30 minutes.

Figure 7. Change in crystallinity at different annealing temperatures

Figure 8. Change in crystallinity at different annealing times

Degree of crystallinity

For every laminate, crystallinity samples were taken before and after annealing. The mean change in crystallinity [%] in relation to the annealing temperature is presented in Figure 7. The mean crystallinity for un-annealed samples is 32.13% after 30 minutes of cure and 29.6% after 60 min. It can be seen that for both curing times, the crystallinity increases significantly with increasing annealing temperatures, whereby the biggest increase is found around the crystallization temperature of the laminate. It is known that crystalline polymers heated to temperatures slightly under melting temperature results in

increased lamellar crystal thickness due to sufficient thermal energy given to the polymer that enables molecular motion [11]. Gogolewski [12] outlines the fact that recrystallization of the polymer proceeds at a faster rate at higher temperatures due to the increase in the number of dislocations in the crystal structure, which forms very favourable nucleation sites. Furthermore, the release of topological constraint and stresses in the amorphous phase at higher temperature promotes crystallization [10]. The thermal energy seems crucial in the annealing process, as temperatures close to the T_g do not show an increase in crystallinity. Gogolewski et al. [12] observed that having a lower annealing temperature reduces the post-processing effectiveness on the nylon-6. For the annealing at 100°C in this study, even a decrease in crystallinity was seen, see Figure 7. This result can not be explained at this moment.

In Figure 8, the change in crystallinity with respect to the annealing time is shown. As can be seen in this graph, no significant effect could be identified. For the annealing study on melt-processed PA-6 [12], experiments were performed at 20-50-60-2000hrs at various temperatures up to 215°C . An incubation period of 10hrs was noted at temperature of 215°C to see a change in the long spacing of SAXS experiments. An even longer incubation time (20hrs) was noted at 200°C after which material properties started to improve significantly. It can therefore be concluded that the results in this study, for the lower annealing temperatures, do not give any significant results at this point, but if the annealing time is increased it might show an increase in polymer properties.

A reduction in the cooling rate after annealing, keeps the polymer chains mobile for a longer duration, which allows more time to form crystals and thus increase the crystallinity of the polymer or increase the level of perfection of the crystals. The cooling rates of the laminates are non-linear, unlike the heating rates to the annealing temperature. As can be seen in Figure 9, the cooling rates show the same trend when plotted against their annealing temperature. In this annealing study, the cooling rate appears to be less significant however, as can be seen in Figure 10. As the polymer chains have sufficient thermal energy for crystal formation during the annealing phase, less can be gained from a slow cooling rate at the end.

Figure 9. Cooling rates at different annealing temperatures.

Figure 10. Change in crystallinity for different cooling rates

As can be concluded from these results, the annealing temperature is the key factor for an increase in crystallinity for both curing times.

Short-beam strength

The results for the short-beam strength with respect to the annealing temperature (see Figure 11) do not show the same trend as for the degree of crystallinity for a cure time of 60 minutes. A peak value of 72.6 MPa was reached for the 60 min cured laminate, compared with the 70.8 MPa obtained with an un-annealed sample. However, for the 30 min cured laminate, the same trend was seen as for the change in crystallinity, going from a baseline of 59.6 MPa to a maximum of 69.32 MPa. The biggest difference between the two cure times is that the fibre-to-matrix bond, its intertwining with the bulk matrix and the degree of branching in the bulk are less for the 30 min cured laminates. It can thus be concluded that the degree of crystallinity is not the only parameter determining the mechanical properties. By annealing, the structure of the polymer chains is improved, the amount of dislocations reduced and a more entangled network formed, leading to a more distinct increase in mechanical properties after annealing a 30 min. cured laminate when compared to a more perfect laminate (60 min of cure).

The same observation was done when looking at the annealing times, see Figure 12. The effect of the annealing time is not significant for the 60 min. cured laminate unlike for the 30 min cured one. For the 30 min. cured samples, the longer the laminate is held at the annealing temperature, the bigger the increase in mechanical properties. After 30 min. of cure, more imperfections will be present in the matrix as well as a lower fibre-to-matrix bond and less branching. The annealing time therefore becomes an important factor in the increase in mechanical properties.

The effect of the cooling rate proved to be insignificant for the mechanical properties, which is in agreement with the results for the change in crystallinity.

Figure 11. Short-beam strength for different annealing temperatures.

Figure 12. Short-beam strength for different annealing times.

CONCLUSIONS

An increase in degree of crystallinity was found with increasing cure time until an equilibrium value was reached. The results were comparable for the pure and the fibre-reinforced APA-6, with a max increase of $\approx 15\%$ after approx. 90 minutes of cure. The mechanical properties followed the same trend, having a peak value (77.4MPa) at the cure time with the maximum degree of crystallinity.

The results for the study on the annealing cycle showed that the change in degree of crystallinity depended mostly on the annealing temperature. The biggest improvement was seen near the crystallization temperature of APA-6 (175°C) with an increase in crystallinity of 20-30%. It was also observed that the mechanical properties only followed the same trend as the crystallinity behaviour for the laminates cured for 30 minutes, leading to a significant improvement in short-beam strength (+17%), as big improvements could be reached with respect to fibre-to-matrix bond and branching of the matrix. As these properties were already attained during curing for a 60 min laminate, their mechanical properties did not show the same trend as its crystallinity after annealing, showing only a slight increase (+3%) in short-beam strength

It could be concluded that the selection of the long cure time is most effective for obtaining good mechanical properties in combination with a high degree of crystallinity. The same properties could be obtained with an annealing cycle, although requiring more time in the mould and more heating energy.

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